

**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY AND
REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIIA: MENTAL HEALTH/PSYCHIATRIC NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A 32 years old Senior High School teacher was knocked down by a motor bike. The facial outlook indicates someone who has been drinking. You have been asked to monitor the client for signs of alcohol withdrawal symptoms

- a. State **TEN (10)** signs and symptoms of alcohol withdrawal symptoms (10 marks)
- b. Mention **SIX (6)** factors that contribute to alcoholism (3 marks)
- c. Describe the nursing management of alcohol withdrawal symptoms within 48 hours (7 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. State **TEN (10)** physical manifestations of Senile Dementia (5 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing management of a patient with senile dementia under the following heading:
 - i. Protection from injury (5 marks)
 - ii. Psychological care (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

- Ai. Mention **TEN (10)** effects of stigmatization on psychiatric patients (10 marks)
- Aii. State **FOUR (4)** measures that can be employed to prevent this stigmatization (4 marks)
- B. State **SIX (6)** functions, duties or roles of a Community Psychiatric Nurse (6 marks)

Total = 20 Marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION (POST BASIC)

DECEMBER 2006

PAPER IB (PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

With the aid of a well labelled diagram covering one-third (1/3) of a page, describe the female external genitalia (the vulva).

Diagram - (4 marks)

Description - (11 marks)

(b) Enumerate FOUR abnormalities of the vulva, excluding pruritus vulvae.
(2 marks)

(c) What advice will you give to a pregnant woman with pruritus vulvae on account of candidiasis
(3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Baby Araba Koomson has been delivered by Caesarean section due to foetal distress.

i) State THREE predisposing causes of foetal distress under each of the following headings:

- i. ante partum (1½ marks)
- ii. intrapartum (1½ marks)

(3 marks)

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QUESTION TWO CONT'D

- (b) Describe the immediate care you will give to baby Koomson.
(14 marks)
- (c) State SIX abnormal observations which must be reported should baby Koomson exhibit any of them.
(3 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Baby Adzeley Addo, a three-day old, was admitted at your clinic with the diagnosis of intracranial haemorrhage.

- (a) Enumerate EIGHT signs that will make you confirm the diagnosis. (4 marks)
 - (b) Describe the management of baby Addo in the first 72 hours. (14 marks)
 - (c) List FOUR possible complications that may occur to baby Addo. (2 marks)
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BEREKUM - GHANA

**REGISTERED MENTAL NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY AND
REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIIIE: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

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BEREKUM - GHANA

QUESTION ONE

A 36 year old woman has been diagnosed with severe anaemia. The doctor has requested blood transfusion for her on admission.

- a. List **TWELVE (12)** specific clinical manifestations she would present. (6 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing responsibilities for the patient before blood transfusion (9 marks)
- c. Describe the nursing care you would give to the patient if she develops fever during the transfusion (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

A 19 year old student is admitted to the medical ward with the diagnosis of bronchial asthma. She complained of dyspnoea and was producing thick tenacious mucus. She looks anxious.

- a. Enumerate **FIVE (5)** precipitating factors of acute asthmatic attack (5 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing care you would give to the patient under:
 - i. Relief of dyspnoea (10 marks)
 - ii. Relief of anxiety (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A 46 year old man who is a known diabetic on your ward has fallen into diabetic coma

- a. What factors may have precipitated to the onset of diabetic coma in the patient? (4 marks)
- b. How would you manage the patient in coma? (8 marks)
- c. What education would you give to the patient on discharge? (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

**REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY
AND REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

FEBRUARY 2016

PAPER IIIIE: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE (3)** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A 30 year old lady was admitted to your ward with the diagnosis of cystitis. She is complaining of supra pubic pain

- a. Enumerate **EIGHT** clinical manifestations of cystitis (4 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing care you would give to the patient to relieve her pain (8 marks)
- c. Describe the education you would give to the patient to prevent recurrent urinary tract infection (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Eric Awadzi, 50, is admitted to the Medical Ward with cerebrovascular accident, CVA. He has left hemiplegia and is semiconscious.

- a. Enumerate **EIGHT** risk factors for the occurrence of CVA. (4 marks)
- b. Describe **EIGHT** clinical features that Mr. Awadzi would present. (4 marks)
- c. Describe how you would manage Mr. Awadzi for the first 48 hours (12 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Madam Aku shika, 30 years was brought to your ward through the casualty with the diagnosis of pneumonia.

- a. Enumerate **TEN (10)** predisposing factors of pneumonia (5 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing intervention she would receive under the following nursing diagnoses
 - i. Ineffective airway clearance (6 marks)
 - ii. Relief of chest pain and discomfort (9 marks)

TOTAL = 20 marks

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**REGISTERED MENTAL NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY AND
REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIIE: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A 36 year old woman has been diagnosed with severe anaemia. The doctor has requested blood transfusion for her on admission.

- a. List **TWELVE (12)** specific clinical manifestations she would present. (6 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing responsibilities for the patient before blood transfusion (9 marks)
- c. Describe the nursing care you would give to the patient if she develops fever during the transfusion (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

A 19 year old student is admitted to the medical ward with the diagnosis of bronchial asthma. She complained of dyspnoea and was producing thick tenacious mucus. She looks anxious.

- a. Enumerate **FIVE (5)** precipitating factors of acute asthmatic attack (5 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing care you would give to the patient under:
 - i. Relief of dyspnoea (10 marks)
 - ii. Relief of anxiety (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A 46 year old man who is a known diabetic on your ward has fallen into diabetic coma

- a. What factors may have precipitated to the onset of diabetic coma in the patient? (4 marks)
- b. How would you manage the patient in coma? (8 marks)
- c. What education would you give to the patient on discharge? (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

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**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING
EXAMINATION - MARCH 2006**

PAPER IIIC (OBSTETRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

(a) Describe the gross structure of the cervix with the aid of a well labelled diagram.
(Diagram should cover one third of a page)

Diagram (4 marks)
Description (8 mark)

(b) List TWO anatomical supports of the cervix. (2 marks)

(c) Enumerate TWO functions of the cervix. (2 marks)

(d) Describe the physiological changes that occur in the cervix during pregnancy.
(4 marks)

QUESTION TWO

As a rotational nurse in the labour ward, you assisted the midwife to deliver a baby with an Apgar score of 6 at 1 minute of birth.

(a) List FOUR characteristics that the baby will present. (4 marks)

(b) How will you manage the baby during the first 10 minutes of birth? (11 marks)

(c) State TEN observations you would make on the baby during the first 2 hours of birth.
(5 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Mrs. Cyndy Bomaa, para 7, was brought to the ward on the first day post delivery with a history of profuse vaginal bleeding and pyrexia.

- (a) Give SIX main causes of secondary post-partum haemorrhage. (4 marks)
 - (b) What will be the immediate management of Mrs. Bomaa to help control the bleeding? (8 marks)
 - (c) What advice would you give to Mrs. Bomaa during the puerperium on the following:
 - i. personal hygiene (6 marks)
 - ii. nutrition (2 marks)
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LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
4TH - 9TH MAY 2005

PAPER I A: PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) With the aid of a well-labelled diagram covering one-third of a page, describe the female external genitalia (the vulva).

Diagram (4 marks)
Description (11 marks)

- (b) Enumerate FOUR abnormalities of the vulva (excluding pruritus vulvae?)
(2 marks)

- (c) What advice will you give to a pregnant woman with pruritus vulvae on account of candidiasis?
(3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Madam Stella Quaison, gravida 5, para 4 all alive, delivered a preterm baby boy weighing 2 kilogram at the maternity wing of your hospital.

- (a) Describe how you would manage baby Quaison under the following headings:

- i. maintenance of body temperature (5 marks)
ii. feeding (5 marks)
iii. prevention of infection (8 marks)

- (b) List TWO favourable and TWO signs of deterioration that baby Quaison may present
(2 marks)

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QUESTION THREE

- a) As a midwife what observations would you make on baby Akua who has discharging eyes after twenty-four hours of birth? (5 marks)
- b) What would be your specific management of baby Akua? (7 marks)
- c) Describe how you would manage baby Akua who was delivered with an Apgar score of five. (8 marks)

QUESTION FOUR.

Baby Yaa Manu is to be discharged home with her mother from Kwesimintsim Hospital 24 hours after delivery.

- (a) Describe the examination to be conducted on baby Yaa before she is sent home. (14 marks)
- (b) How does the ovarian hormone oestrogen influence the young girl at puberty? (6 marks)
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QUESTION TWO CONT'D

C-1. Madam Josephine Ako 25 years old , G2 P1 at term, was brought to the labour ward in labour on the 1st of May, 2005 at 8.00am for admission. Using the partograph provided plot the following observations made on Madam Josephine Ako.

Time: 8.00am (Admission)

- Cervical dilatation - 3CM
- Descent of foetal head - 4/5th
- Uterine contractions -3 in 10 mins lasting between 20-40secs
- Membranes - Intact
- Foetal Heart rate - 130b.p.m
- Moulding - +

9:30 -10.30am

- Foetal Heart - 134 b.p.m.
- Contractions -3 in 10 mins lasting between 20 - 40 seconds

10:30 -11:30 am

- Foetal Heart - 132 b.p.m
- Contractions -4 in 10 mins lasting between 20 -40 seconds

12 noon

- Cervical dilatation - 6cm
- Descent of foetal head - 2/5th
- Uterine contraction - 4 in 10 mins. lasting over 40 seconds
- Foetal Heart Rate - 134 b p m
- Moulding - ++

(6marks)

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION (BASIC)

DECEMBER 2006

PAPER 1A (PAEDIATRICS, OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

(a) With the aid of a well labelled diagram covering one third (1/3) of a page, describe the perineal body under the following headings:

- i. position, shape and size (3 marks)
- ii. structure and functions (4 marks)

Description (7 marks)
Diagram (3 marks)
Total (10 marks)

Stella Quaison, an adolescent primipara, delivered at home and was brought to the hospital. On examination, it was discovered that she has sustained second degree perineal tear.

(b) Describe the care of the wound under the following headings:

- i. at the hospital (6 marks)
- ii. home for the first 2 weeks (4 marks)

QUESTION TWO

(a) Describe FOUR factors that may cause a pregnant woman to deliver a congenitally abnormal baby. Give one example of the condition that each factor may cause.
(8 marks)

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

- (b) How can a midwife help reduce the risk of having a congenitally abnormal baby? (12 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- (a) As a midwife, what observation would you make on baby Yaa who has discharging eyes after twenty-four hours of birth? (5 marks)
- (b) What would be your specific management of baby Yaa? (7 marks)
- (c) Describe how you would manage baby Yaa who was delivered with an Apgar score of five. (8 marks)

QUESTION FOUR

- (a) Describe the umbilical cord/funis. (No diagram required) (7 marks)
- (b) Mrs. Mensah, a primipara, delivered 24 hours ago. What advice will you give her on how to care for the umbilical cord to prevent infection? (6 marks)
- (c) Describe SEVEN ways in which a new-born baby can be prevented from injury and accident in the hospital. (7 marks)
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**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING, REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING AND
REGISTERED MENTAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIIC: OBSTETRIC NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

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ACCRA - GHANA

QUESTION ONE

- a. With a well labelled diagram covering $\frac{1}{3}$ of a page, describe the macroscopic structure of the fallopian tube.
- i. Diagram (3 marks)
 - ii. Description (10 marks)
- b. State **FIVE (5)** relations of the fallopian tube (5 marks)
- c. State the nerve supply and supports of the Fallopian tube (2 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Client G2 P0 12 weeks amenorrhoea reported at your facility with the history of slight vaginal bleeding and lower abdominal pains. She was diagnosed as having threatened abortion.

- a. State **FIVE (5)** causes of abortion (5 marks)
- b. How would you manage the patient from the time of admission till she is discharged. (10 marks)
- c. State **FIVE (5)** outcomes of threatened abortion. (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

- A. A 33-year old Para 6^{AA} woman was brought to your facility with her baby after 48 hours of delivery at home. Her temperature on examination was 39.2^{oC}, pulse was 102 beat per minute and her blood pressure read $\frac{130}{70}$ mmHg. She was diagnosed as having puerperal pyrexia.
- i. Describe how you would manage the above woman? (10 marks)
 - ii. How would you manage her baby's cord? (6 marks)
- B. How would you educate the woman on Lactational Amenorrhoea Method (LAM)? (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

**REGISTERED MENTAL NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY AND
REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIIF: SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Following a laparotomy to remove a tumour from the abdomen, Mr. Owusu Ansah was brought to the ward in a state of shock. Mr. Owusu Ansah is however conscious.

- a. How would you explain the term shock? (4 marks)
- b. State **EIGHT (8)** symptoms that the patient would present. (4 marks)
- c. Describe how you would manage Mr. Ansah on the ward. (12 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

A road traffic accident victim is admitted to the ward with a compound fracture of the right tibia and fibula. He is for closed reduction and application of **PLASTER OF PARIS (P.O.P)** cast.

- a. Enumerate **FIVE (5)** signs and symptoms of compound fracture. (5 marks)
- b. Describe how you would prepare the patient physically for the operation. (8 marks)
- c. Describe how you would provide care for the patient with regard to the P.O.P (7 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Ms. Mercy Acquah, an 18 year old student is admitted to the surgical ward for tonsillectomy.

- a. List **FIVE (5)** indications for the Surgery. (5 marks)
- b. How would you educate the patient on selfcare post operatively? (6 marks)
- c. Describe the **SPECIFIC** post operative nursing care that will be given to Mercy within the first 24 hours. (9 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION**DECEMBER 2006****PAPER IIB (MIDWIFERY)****ESSAY**

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOUR

QUESTION ONE

Madam Shormeh Dowuona, , 35 year old primigravida, is admitted into the antenatal ward on account of feeling unwell, oedema and a blood pressure of 160/100 mmHg. Urine test revealed proteinuria. She is diagnosed as having severe pre-eclampsia.

- (a) Describe how Madam Dowuona will be managed for the first three days on admission.
(10 marks)
- (b) Outline the nursing intervention if Madam Dowuona shows signs of impending eclampsia.
(7 marks)
- (c) State SIX possible complications which Madam Kesewaa is exposed to if she gets attacks of fits?
(3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Madam Esi Atta, Gravida 2 Para 1, was referred to your hospital by a private

- 2 -

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

(b) State the deviations in labour that can be detected on any partograph concerning:

- i. the condition of baby (4 marks)
- ii. condition of mother (2 marks)
- iii. progress of labour (3 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Madam Oyoe Quartey, a primi-para reported at the emergency room with a history of passing a clot which was followed by heavy bleeding about an hour ago, 3 days post spontaneous vaginal delivery at home.

(a) Mention THREE causes of Madam Quartey's condition. (3 marks)

(b) What will be your management for the first 24 hours of:

- i. Madam Quartey (7 marks)
- ii. Baby Quartey (5 marks)

(c) State FIVE disadvantages of home delivery. (5 marks)

**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING, REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING AND
REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

FEBRUARY 2016

PAPER IIIC: OBSTETRIC NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Rosemond G1 P0 34 weeks pregnant delivered few hours ago at your facility. Describe how you would manage the baby under the following headings.

- ai. Warmth (5 marks)
- aii. Prevention of infection (5 marks)
- b. State **TEN** causes of preterm labour. (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- A. Describe the past obstetrical history that would be obtained from Madam Aku Abbey, G2 P1, 24 weeks pregnant who has come to the antenatal clinic (10 marks)
- B. State **FIVE** observations each that you will make on
 - i. A primigravida who had a spontaneous delivery with a sutured episiotomy (5 marks)
 - ii. A baby who was spontaneously delivered (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A woman G1 P0 has been admitted to your ward with the diagnosis of Ruptured Ectopic pregnancy.

- a. State the signs and symptoms that the woman will exhibit. (6 marks)
- b. State **FOUR** investigations that will be requested. (2 marks)
- c. Describe the pre-operative procedure for this woman till she is taken to the theatre. (12 marks)

Total = 20 marks

STATE REGISTERED MIDWIFERY EXAMINATION
7TH-11TH MAY, 2001

PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY
PAPER I 'B' - ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) Draw a large well labelled diagram covering about one-third ($\frac{1}{3}$) of a page of the maternal surface of the placenta at term. (4 marks)
- (b) Describe the placenta at term under the following headings:
(i) Shape
(ii) Size
(iii) Weight
(iv) Gross structure of placenta and membranes. (11 marks)
- (c) Describe velamentous insertion of cord. (2 marks)
- (d) State THREE possible effects of velamentous insertion of cord on the foetus during pregnancy and labour. (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Baby Abo Mansah has been delivered by Caesarean Section due to foetal distress.

- (a) Describe the care you will give to baby Mansah using the following headings:
(i) Immediate care (12 marks)
(ii) Subsequent care on the ward (5 marks)
- (b) State SIX abnormal observations which must be reported to the doctor should baby Abo Mansah exhibit any of them. (3 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- (a) Describe uterine contractions in true labour. (8 marks)
- (b) Describe the signs and symptoms of intra-cranial injury in a neonate after a difficult vaginal delivery under the headings stated below.
(i) Respiratory system (2 marks)
(ii) Nervous system (5 marks)
- 2 marks

What other observations would you make on a baby with intra-

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FINAL MIDWIFERY EXAMINATION - 1ST-5TH NOVEMBER, 1999
PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

PAPER I 'B' - ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED:

QUESTION ONE

With the aid of a well labelled diagram covering half a page

- Describe the vulva as seen on vaginal examination of a labouring woman. (16 marks)
- State FOUR abnormal conditions which can be seen in the vulva of a pregnant woman and give their causes. (4 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Baby Sika was born at term, and weighed 3kg., but had an Apgar score of 4 at 1 minute of birth. Its skin appeared dusky in colour and it failed to cry. Apex beat was 58 bpm.

- Describe your management of Baby Sika for the first thirty minutes of its life. (14 marks)
- List FOUR foetal and FOUR maternal conditions which may result in asphyxia neonatorum. (4 marks)
- State FOUR complications of asphyxia neonatorum. (2 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- Describe the Fallopian Tube as can be seen with the naked eye. (10 marks)
- Describe how you will manage an active 1.8kg. preterm baby on the district for the first three days of delivery - using the topics below:
 - Maintenance of body temperature. (2 marks)

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION

MARCH 2018

PAPER I: PAEDIATRICS, OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY TEST

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

N/S

QUESTION ONE

- a. With a well labelled diagram describe the placenta at term. (10 marks)
- b. State the function of the placenta under the following headings.
 - i. Respiration (2 marks)
 - ii. Protection (2 marks)
- c. Describe the pathological conditions of the placenta. (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- A. Madam Bobor reported at your clinic with her 6-month old baby who had a cleft palate repaired three days ago. She complained that the baby was not able to breastfeed. How would you educate Madam Bobor under the following headings:
 - i. Nutrition (3 marks)
 - ii. Oral hygiene (2 marks)
 - iii. Restrains (2 marks)
- B. Describe the following parts of the foetal skull.
 - i. Anterior fontanelle (6 marks)
 - ii. Posterior fontanelle (4 marks)
- C. Explain caput succedaneum to a first year student midwife. (3 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. Describe the changes that take place in the breast during pregnancy. (8 marks)
- b. How would you teach a new mother to position and attach her baby to the breast? (8 marks)
- c. State **EIGHT (8)** disadvantages of artificial feeding. (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- a. Describe the macroscopic structure of the fallopian tubes.
(no diagram required) (12 marks)
- b. State the functions of the fallopian tubes. (4 marks)
- c. State the supports/relations of the fallopian tubes. (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION

FEBRUARY 2017

PAPER II: MIDWIFERY

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Akweley Anim G2P1^A reported at the labour ward with the history of delayed 2nd twin. On examination, the membranes were intact. Abdominal palpation reveals longitudinal lie with cephalic presentation.

- a. How would you manage Madam Anim in the 2nd stage of labour. (15 marks)
(Trolley already set)
- b. State **FIVE (5)** complications associated with twin pregnancy. (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Eunice Lartey G4 P3^{AA} who is 30 weeks pregnant was brought to the district hospital with the history of bleeding per vaginum, which started when she woke up from bed. Her vitals signs were normal and her history shows that she is having antepartum haemorrhage.

- a. **State** and **explain** the major types of placenta praevia. (8 marks)
- b. Describe the management of Madam Eunice Lartey in the hospital. (12 marks)
- c. Enumerate **TWO (2)** effects **each** of antepartum haemorrhage on the mother and baby. (2 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Maame Yaa Aboagye, a 34 year-old mother of three reported at the antenatal clinic with a history of 18 weeks amenorrhoea, nausea and vomiting and the passage of vesicles per vaginum.

- a. What other signs and symptoms will help you arrive at a diagnosis if you suspect hydatidiform mole? (5 marks)
- b. Describe your management under the following :
 - i. Before evacuation (7 marks)
 - ii. After the evacuation till discharge (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

.../2

QUESTION FOUR

Afah Minat, G2 P2^{AA} delivered 48 hours ago at your facility. She has shown interest to use intrauterine contraceptive device.

- a. i. What education will you give to Afah Minat to enable her use the device? (6 marks)
- ii. What information will you give her on personal hygiene? (4 marks)
- b. Outline the care you will give to Afah Minat during the seven (7) days postnatal visit. (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

RM

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION

AUGUST 2015

PAPER II: MIDWIFERY

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A 32 year old G2P1^A 34 weeks pregnant woman was rushed to your facility and was diagnosed as having placental abruption.

- a. Describe how you would manage the client with the above condition. (12 marks)
- b. What clinical manifestations would the client present? (6 marks)
- c. Mention **FOUR** complications that may occur in placental abruption. (2 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Aku Shika, G 6 P5^{AA} delivered soon on arrival at your labour ward. The baby weighed 3.6kgs. She was later found to be bleeding and in a state of collapse two hours after delivery.

- a. Give **EIGHT (8)** possible causes of Mary's condition. (4 marks)
- b. Describe your management of her condition till the bleeding is controlled. (12 marks)
- c. Give **FOUR (4)** preventive measures of Post-Partum Haemorrhage during labour. (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Madam Eliaso, 32 weeks pregnant, and a non attendant was brought to the hospital, with elevated temperature. On further assessment by the doctor she was diagnosed as having uncomplicated malaria.

- a. Describe how Madam Eliaso would be managed for the uncomplicated malaria. (9 marks)
- b. Describe the education that you would give her on discharge. (8 marks)
- c. State **THREE (3)** complications each of malaria in pregnancy to the mother and baby. (3 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

Madam Ayishetu Mahamadu G3P2^{AA}, 36 weeks pregnant had her two previous deliveries through Caesarean Section. She is booked for an elective section for the third time.

- a. State **TEN (10)** indications for Caesarean Section. (5 marks)
- b. How would you prepare Madam Ayishetu for the surgery? (7 marks)
- ci. Describe the post operative management for the first 72 hours. (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION (BASIC)

AUGUST 2017

PAPER II: MIDWIFERY

ESSAY TEST

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question carries **20 marks**.
3. Read the questions carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
4. Do not write in either margin.
5. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract marks.

QUESTION ONE

Madam Asana Boabeng 42 weeks G1P0 has been admitted to your facility for induction of labour

- a. Explain the indications for the above procedure. (8 marks)
- b. State **FIVE (5)** contra indications of induction of labour. (5 marks)
- c. Describe the midwives responsibilities during induction of labour. (7 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Maame Ama Karikari, a 19 year old student was brought to the hospital by her grandmother with the history of attempted termination of her 16 weeks pregnancy. On examination the abdomen was tender, pulse was rapid, temperature high and some products of conception seen on speculum examination. She was diagnosed as having inevitable abortion.

- a. Describe the management of Maame Ama Karikari. (12 marks)
- b. Outline the measures you would take to prevent Ama Karikari from encountering a similar problem. (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Daavi Obiri, 32 weeks pregnant, and a non attendant was brought to the hospital, with pyrexia. On further assessment by the doctor she was diagnosed as having uncomplicated malaria.

- a. Describe how Daavi Obiri would be managed for the uncomplicated malaria. (12 marks)
- b. Describe the education you would give her on discharge. (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

Madam Ama Banda, a 32 year old primigravida, who is 36 weeks pregnant is admitted to your facility with the history of severe pre-eclampsia. She started fitting as soon as she was admitted. Her blood pressure was 240/120 mmHg.

- a. How would you manage Madam Banda? (12 marks)
- b. What advice would you give to her and the family before discharge from the hospital? (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION

FEBRUARY 2017

PAPER I: PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- a. State **TEN (10)** signs and symptoms of intracranial injury. (5 marks)
- b. Describe how you will nurse a baby with intracranial injury in the hospital for the first 24 hours (10 marks)
- c. How will a midwife prevent injury to a baby during delivery? (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- A. Describe the physiological changes that take place to control haemorrhage after delivery. (12 marks)
- B. i. State **EIGHT (8)** indications that a midwife may consider before giving episiotomy. (4 marks)
- ii. What education will you give to a mother who has just had her episiotomy repaired? (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. Describe the macroscopic structure of the urinary bladder. (10 marks)
(No diagram required)
- b. What are the effects of full bladder in labour. (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- a. Describe the gross structure of the cervix uteri. (10 marks)
(No diagram required)
- b. What changes occur in the cervix during
- i. Pregnancy (7 marks)
- ii. Labour (3 marks)

Total = 20 marks

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REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION (BASIC)

FEBRUARY 2016

PAPER II: MIDWIFERY

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mrs. Emefa Ablordey, a 32 year old primigravida, who is 36 weeks pregnant was admitted to your facility with the history of severe pre-eclampsia. She started fitting as soon as she was admitted. Her blood pressure was $^{240}/_{120}$ mmHG.

- a. How would you manage Mrs. Ablordey? (12 marks)
- b. What advice would you give her and her family before discharge from the hospital? (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Mrs. Alimatu Fuseni 40 years old Gravida 4 Para 3^{AA} was admitted to your labour ward on 3rd January 2016 at 3:30 am with a history of labour pains. Her hospital number is 3/01/16. According to her, membranes ruptured on the 2nd January at 2:30 am.

- a. Plot the observations attached on the partograph sheet provided (11 marks)
- b. State **NINE (9)** signs and symptoms in case Madam Alimatu experiences maternal distress (9 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Madam Adjoa Maanu, a 25 year old multipara of two, came to the ANC clinic with 28 weeks pregnancy. On physical examination, her conjunctiva, lips, tongue and palms were pale. She was diagnosed as having anaemia in pregnancy.

- a. State **TEN** causes of anaemia in pregnancy. (5 marks)
- b. Describe how anaemia can be prevented in pregnancy. (12 marks)
- c. State **THREE** complications each of anaemia in pregnancy under the following headings:
 - i. Mother
 - ii. Foetus

(3 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

Madam Adisa Wala, a 34- year-old mother of three children reported at the antenatal clinic with a history of 18 weeks amenorrhoea, nausea and vomiting and the passage of vesicles per vaginum.

- a. What other signs and symptoms will help you arrive at a diagnosis if you suspect hydatidiform mole (5 marks)
- b. Describe your nursing interventions :
 - i. Before the evacuation (7 marks)
 - ii. After the evacuation till discharge (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION

MARCH 2018

PAPER II: MIDWIFERY

ESSAY TEST

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

N/S

QUESTION ONE

Mrs. Shetu Aweah G5 P4^{AA} has just given birth to a baby boy on your ward.

- a. Describe how you would manage the third stage of labour. (10 marks)
- b. State **SIX (6)** complications that may occur as a result of mismanagement of this stage of labour. (6 marks)
- c. State **EIGHT (8)** signs which a woman with atony uterus would exhibit. (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a i. Explain the term puerperal sepsis. (2 marks)
- a ii. Name two organisms that cause puerperal sepsis with two examples each. (4 marks)
- b. State **SEVEN (7)** signs and symptoms of puerperal sepsis. (7 marks)
- c. How would you manage a woman who has been admitted with puerperal sepsis? (7 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. Explain cord prolapse and its causes. (6 marks)
- b. Describe how you would manage a client with cord prolapse. (14 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

QUESTION FOUR

Mrs. Akosua Myles, 28-years-old G 6 P 5^{AA} had an emergency caesarean section on account of multiple pregnancy (**triplets**).

- a. Describe your management of Mrs. Myles under the following headings:
 - i. Immediate post-operative care (5 marks)
 - ii. Care at the postnatal ward (6 marks)
- b. What education would you give to Mrs. Myles on discharge? (9 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION

AUGUST 2015

PAPER I: PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- a. With the aid of a well labelled diagram covering one-third of a page, describe the gross structure of the cervix uteri.
- i. Diagram (3 marks)
 - ii. Description (7 marks)
- b. What changes occur in the cervix during
- i. Pregnancy (7 marks)
 - ii. Labour (3 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Mrs. Doris Annan a Primigravida, 26 weeks gestation came to your facility and complained of a thick vaginal discharge which is cheese-like in appearance and causes pruritis of the vulva and vagina. She was diagnosed as having candidiasis.

- a. State other **FOUR (4)** vaginal infections you would look out for during Antenatal Care (2 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing management for Mrs. Doris Annan (8 marks)
- c. Describe the changes that occur in the vagina during pregnancy (6 marks)
- d. Explain how the vagina prevents infection on its own (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A two-day old baby was brought to your facility and was diagnosed as having ophthalmia neonatorum.

- a. Enumerate **SIX (6)** causative organisms of ophthalmia neonatorum (3 marks)
- b. Describe how the baby would be managed to prevent complications (12 marks)
- c. State **FIVE (5)** preventive measures to reduce the occurrence of ophthalmia neonatorum (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- A. Identify **FIVE (5)** differences between cephalhaematoma and caput succedaneum (5 marks)
- B. Amniotic fluid is very important for the fetus. (5 marks)
- i. Explain **TEN (10)** functions of the amniotic fluid (10 marks)
 - ii. State **TEN (10)** compositions of the amniotic fluid (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION (BASIC)

JANUARY 2009

PAPER I: PAEDIATRICS, OBSTETRICS ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY

Answer all four questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

(a) With the aid of a well-labelled diagram covering one-third (1/3) of a page, describe the cross-section of the umbilical cord.

Diagram - (3 marks)
Description - (8 marks)

(b) Mention and explain the significance of abnormalities in the following structures on the foetus:

i. length of cord (3 marks)

ii. quantity of amniotic fluid (3 marks)

(c) Outline THREE functions of the amniotic fluid in labour. (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Ms. Pinky, aged 18 years, delivered in your facility and was worried about the long shape of her baby's head.

- (a) What explanation will you give to allay her anxiety? (Not more than 30 words)
(3 marks)
- (b) Explain FIVE differences between cephal haematoma and caput succedaneum. (10 marks)
- (c) i. Outline THREE observations that should be noted when the newborn baby's head is examined after birth. (3 marks)
- ii. What will be the specific management of a baby with a cephal haematoma? (4 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Madam Bedjo delivered a male infant with jaundice and was diagnosed as having haemolytic disease of the new born.

- (a) Explain the term, haemolytic disease of the new born (in not more than 30 words). (2 marks)
- (b) State FOUR causes of haemolytic jaundice. (2 marks)
- (c) Describe the specific role of the midwife under the following headings:
- i. during exchange blood transfusion (10 marks)
- ii. after exchange blood transfusion (6 marks)

QUESTION FOUR

- (a) Describe the microscopic structure of the vagina (No diagram required). (10 marks)
- (b) Describe the changes that occur in the vagina during pregnancy. (6 marks)
- (c) Explain how the vagina prevents infection on its own. (4 marks)
-

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION

AUGUST 2016

PAPER I: PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the questions carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- a. Describe the innominate bone (No diagram required). (12 marks)
- b. Enumerate **FOUR (4)** pelvic joints. (2 marks)
- c. How would you determine the adequacy of the female pelvis during antenatal care? (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. State **FOUR (4)** indications of Exchange Blood Transfusion for an infant at the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). (4 marks)
- b. Describe the **SPECIFIC** role of the midwife under the following headings:
 - i. During exchange blood transfusion (10 marks)
 - ii. After exchange blood transfusion (4 marks)
- c. List **FOUR (4)** complications of exchange blood transfusion. (2 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Madam Adjoa Banda delivered a baby girl some few hours ago.

- a. How would you perform examination of her baby? (12 marks)
- b. Describe how you would teach Madam Banda to express and save breast milk for the baby's use. (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- a. What are the features of cephalhaematoma? (5 marks)
- b. Explain **TEN (10)** functions of amniotic fluid. (10 marks)
- c. State **TEN (10)** compositions of the amniotic fluid. (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION (BASIC)

FEBRUARY 2016

PAPER I: PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

1. Describe the microscopic structure of the vagina (No diagram required) (10 marks)
- b. Describe the changes that occur in the vagina during pregnancy (6 marks)
- c. Explain how the vagina prevents infection on its own (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Emefa Bansah a Primipara, delivered three weeks after her expected date of delivery. The baby was diagnosed as post maturity.

- a. State **TEN (10)** indications that cause induction of labour in post maturity. (10 marks)
- b. Describe how you would examine the baby after delivery (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A. Describe the changes that takes place in the uterus after delivery under the following headings.

- i. Inner lining of the uterus (5 marks)
- ii. Myometrium (5 marks)

Bi. State **SIX** questions that you would enquire form Madam Mensah who has come to your clinic for 6 weeks post natal examination. (6 marks)

.Bii. State **FOUR** things you would look for during Madam Mensah's vaginal examination. (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- A. Describe the characteristics of the **Four (4)** main types of pelvis (12 marks)
- B. State **EIGHT** indications that a midwife may consider before giving episiotomy. (4 marks)
- C. What education would you give to a mother who has just had her episiotomy repaired? (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

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NMC, BETHUN

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION (BASIC)

AUGUST 2017

PAPER I: PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY TEST

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question carries **20 marks**.
3. Read the questions carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
4. Do not write in either margin.
5. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract marks.

LIBRARY
NMC, BETHUN

QUESTION ONE

- a. With a well labelled diagram covering about 1/3 of a page draw and describe the perineal body.
- i. Diagram (4 marks)
 - ii. Description (8 marks)
- b. Describe how you would prevent damage to the pelvic floor muscle during labour. (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- A. Describe how you would manage a baby who is undergoing phototherapy. (12 marks)
- B. State **EIGHT (8)** measures you would put in place to prevent infections in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A mother delivered a baby with a birth weight of 3kg who could not breathe at birth.

- a. How would you prepare for the resuscitation of the baby? (6 marks)
- b. Describe the resuscitation of the baby. (11 marks)
- c. List **SIX (6)** contributory factors of the baby's poor condition at birth. (3 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- A. What are the changes that occur in the female during puberty under the influence of oestrogen? (8 marks)
- B. How would you educate a woman who want to use Calendar Based Method for family planning. (12 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION

AUGUST 2016

PAPER II: MIDWIFERY

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the questions carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Study the attached Partograph on Mrs. Morkor Laryea and interperate the following.

- a. Progress of labour from 9:30 am – 12:30 pm (4 marks)
- b. Fetal condition from 6:00 am – 9:30 am (4 marks)
- c. Maternal condition from 7:00 am – 10:30 am (4 marks)
- d. How would you prepare the woman for caesarean section? (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- A. Describe the prevention of Post Partum Haemorrhage (PPH) during:
 - i. Pregnancy (6 marks)
 - ii. Labour (8 marks)
- B. How would you manage breast engorgement within the first week of delivery? (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Madam Okiki 37 weeks pregnant reported at the labour ward with lower abdominal and waist pain and the presence of show.

- a. As a midwife how would you conduct vaginal examination on Madam Okiki? (10 marks)
- b. List **FOUR (4)** indications for vaginal examination. (4 marks)
- c. What observations are made during vaginal examinations? **(State SIX (6) only)** (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

A 30 year old GP1P0 reported at the antenatal clinic with a history of 18 weeks amenorrhoea. She complained of persistent vomiting, she looked dehydrated and very worried. She was diagnosed as having hyperemesis gravidarum.

- a. Outline the differences between hyperemesis gravidarum and vomiting in early pregnancy. (4 marks)
- b. Describe the management you will give to this patient. (12 marks)
- c. List **FOUR (4)** complications of hyperemesis gravidarum. (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

Name: Mrs. Morker Langer

Age: 37

Hospital number: 541116

Date of admission: 24/8/16

Time of admission: 6^{am}

Ruptured membranes: 1 hours

Gravida: 3 Para: 2AA

EDD: 31/8/16

Gestation (wks): 39 weeks

Amniotic fluid	I	I	C		C
Moulding	0	0	+		++

Oxytocin U/L					
Crpps/min					

Drugs given and IV fluids

Temp °C	37.8		37.9		38.0
---------	------	--	------	--	------

Urine	protein	Nil	Nil	Nil	+
	acetone	Nil	Nil	Nil	+
	volume	100ml	50ml	100ml	100ml

